

DESIGN AND SIMULATION ANALYSIS OF FRICTION STIR WELDING USING ANSYS

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ABSTRACT

For materials like aluminium that are notoriously difficult to weld, FSW provides a stable-state solution that produces very good welds. The main goal of this project is to investigate the energy and hardness of friction stir welded aluminium alloy and copper at different speeds utilising a taper-effect pin profile. High carbon high chromium cloth is the material of choice for the enforcement. A computer numerically controlled milling machine (CNC) with a cutting speed of 700 rpm is used for the experimental inquiry. ANSYS is used to conduct a finite element analysis (FEA) of 700 rpm friction stir welding of aluminium 6061 and aluminium 5083. We do structural and thermal analysis. Pro/Engineer now has a parametric version that includes the cutting tool and weld plates. For this assessment, we looked at the results of friction stir welding with taper and round force pin profiles.

1. INTRODUCTION

As an alternate novel joining technology, friction stir welding (FSW) has been employed for high-quality production since 1996. A fantastic weld is produced as joining does not take place at temperatures higher than the fabric's melting point. This quality eliminates solidification flaws and drastically lessens the harmful effects of excessive heat entry, such as distortion. In addition to being very eco-friendly, friction stir welding doesn't release any fumes and doesn't need filler fabric, which results in this way environmentally excellent. The modern section in FSW studies has been aimed in the direction of growing the usefulness of this

Method in high-melting-temperature materials, such as carbon and stainless steels as well as nickel-based alloys, by developing a structure that can withstand the high pressures and temperatures required of these materials.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

In a study that focused on performing Friction Stir Welding (FSW) on polymeric materials, Nelson, Sorenson, and Johns (2004) found significant findings. We rely on polymeric materials for a wide variety of tasks in our daily lives, say Callister and Rethwisch (2011). The final result is the determining factor in categorising various polymers. One example of a polymer is plastic, which is used extensively in our dynamic world. Plastics are ubiquitous because of their exceptional structural strength. One readily available aspect of plastics is their versatility in meeting client demands via a wide range of possible combination qualities. In the FSW method, a portion of the joint is plasticized to resist the non-consumable instrument or probe that is inserted into the joint site, creating a thermal gradient between the probe and the hostile amounts present in the joint (Nelson et al., 2003). After that, the probe is either translated along the joint or removed to allow the plasticized parts to harden before joining.

According to the research done by Nelson et al. (2003),

definitely a patent invention which pertains to away and apparatus of becoming a member of thermoplastic substances. There are goals from this invention which are representing constraints surface that is desk bound/movements independently of the pin and introducing energy by a machine unbiased of the frictional strength produced by the tool. This brought about the development of Aluminium-fashion tool with hot shoe tool layout being used on the thermoplastic. In this method, the constraining floor is in at least in element insulated to lessen the dissipation of the heat from the weld area. Process parameters were additionally being monitored (spindle speed, feed rate, profile device) in which by means of the analysis of every parameter are proven from the result acquired through mechanical checking out. Based on the result obtained, the most beneficial system parameters for engaging in friction stir welding (FSW) on thermoplastic materials are as follow.

3. MATERIAL AND METHODS

For this challenge, we used HCHCr (High Carbon High Chromium metallic) Aluminium alloy 7475 for the device material and aluminium composite 7475 and Al 6061 for the artwork pieces. These alloys combine the best of both worlds, with high electric conductivity and excellent intake resistance. These amalgams are great combinations for use at low temperatures. They perform best when exposed to temperatures below freezing and degrade when exposed to temperatures above freezing. Amalgams made of aluminium are unstable at temperatures between 200 and 250 degrees Celsius (392 and 482 degrees Fahrenheit). You may see a schematic of the Aluminum/Aluminum 7475 composite in the datasheet that is attached. Musical composition Within the, the process of introducing the Aluminum/Aluminum 7475 amalgam is outlined.

desk that goes with it.

Element	Content (%)
Aluminum, Al	90.3
Zinc, Zn	5.7
Magnesium, Mg	2.3
Silicon, Si	1.50
Chromium, Cr	0.22

Physical Properties

Cold Working

Customary techniques are applied to directly cool paintings Aluminum/Aluminum 7475 amalgam within the bolstered condition.

Framing

Aluminum/Aluminum 7475 compound can be framed utilizing traditional strategies. This compound can be efficaciously framed inside the tempered condition than inside the warmth treated condition wherein the aggregate has all of the greater spring gain in mild of its fine.

Mach failure

Aluminum/Aluminum 7475 amalgam has extraordinary machining features within the bolstered situation. Oil base greases may be applied in the course of the machining activities of this amalgam.

Warmth Treatment

Aluminum/Aluminum 7475 amalgam can be warmed with it.

Steel Properties

Physical Properties

The following table shows the physical properties of Aluminium / Aluminum 7475 alloy.

Properties	Metric	Imperial
Density	2.6-2.8 g/cm ³	0.0839-0.1011 lb/in ³
Melting point	546°C	1015°F

D3 Steel having homes of High Carbon 2% and High Chromium 12% equipment steel with excessive put on competition. Its supply condition is soft toughened to simple machining which prescribe hardness is fifty seven-fifty eight HRC with in the wake of creating the kick the bucket and contraptions.

Physical Properties

Coefficient of thermal expansion / °C	20	25	30	340	350	360	370
10 ⁻⁶ / °C	23	23	23	24	24	24	24
Thermal Conductivity / °C	30	35	40				
W/mK	167	167	167				

OBJECTIVE AND METHODOLOGY

The target of the current exploration is to build up a confined aspect reenactment with improved ability to anticipate nice developmental aluminum compounds and Al 6061. To determine the best weld boundaries utilizing sample line condition. Examinations have been led on the AA 7475 and Al 6061 out of a vertical hub CNC processing machine through programming at numerous cutting gear (round, rectangular and tighten). In this project to explore the mechanical residences, as an instance, pliable, hardness and effect.

Methodology

- In this paintings frictional blend welded Pure Aluminium 7475 and Al 6061 examples are checked out for mechanical houses. In this examination FSW examples are set up at 11mm/min feed price and speeds are 750rpm.
- In this test plate size of aluminum and Al 6061 are identical and having 100mm period, 50mm width and 5mm thickness. H13 device metal material is carried out to provide the gadgets. Apparatus has pin distance throughout of 6 millimeter duration. Instrument measurements: Shoulder Diameter-18mm, Pin Diameter 6mm
- The 3-D demonstrating of FSW is based totally in Pro/Engineer.
- In static examination, to decide the pressure, stress and misshapening.

4. MODELING AND ANALYSIS

Introduction to CAD

The use of personal computers for the purpose of creating and documenting plans is known as computer-aided design (CAD), also abbreviated as computer-assisted structure and drawing (CADD). The steps of using a computer to draft are laid out in PC Aided Drafting. Customers are provided with information devices to clean up format systems, documentation, and collecting systems via CADD programming or events. A common use case for computer-aided design (CADD) output is computerised assessments of print or machining carrying occurrences. Improvements in enterprise-level programming (such as manufacturing, improvement, and others) are directly correlated with the advancements made by CADD-based authoring laptop programmes. typically use vector-based (directly) events, while practical-based programming uses raster-based certainly (pixelated) events. Exceptional alternatives to forms are often included in CADD conditions. Consistent with application-unambiguous suggestions, CAD output must exclude records such as materials, systems, estimates, and protections, just as in the human drafting of structural and specific drawings.

Combining curves and figures in a two-

dimensional (2D) space is possible with the use of a PC-supported plan, as are twists, surfaces, and solids in a three-dimensional (3D) object. Your element design needs will remain the same regardless of the level of your project; regardless of the amount of time you have, you will benefit from the historical, user-friendly, moderate workflow that Pro/ENGINEER provides.

2D blueprint

Fig.1: Two-dimensional sketch and three-dimensional model of pipe

virtual tool

Figure 2: Tool Assembly 3D Model

Figure 3: Assembly using a 3D model

ANSYS

ANSYS is comprehensively precious constrained section assessment (FEA) programming percent. Constrained Element Analysis is a numerical device for constructing an exceptional form into little ornobits (of consumer allotted length) referred to as segments. The object executes conditions that supervise the lead of those segments and comprehends all of them; making an in depth clarification of methods the device is going approximately commonly. These effects by using then can be shown in taken care of out, or graphical structures. Such an assessment is normally used for the arrangement and smoothing out of a gadget extraordinarily complicated to separate with the aid of hand. Systems that may match into this magnificence are unnecessarily erratic due to their geometry, scale, or regulating situations.

asan instance, tables, charts, and structure plots.

STATIC ANALYSIS OF FRICTION STIR WELDING PROCESS

Case 1: ROUND TOOL

Imported model

Meshing model

BOUNDARYCONDITIONS

AT SPEED-700

RPMTOTALDEFORMA

TION

EQUIVALENTSTRESS

EQUVALENTSTRAIN AT SPEED-1000 RPMTOTALDEFORMATION

EQUVALENTSTRESS

EQUVALENTSTRAIN

AT SPEED-1200

RPMTOTALDEFORMA

TION

Case2:TAPERTOOLAT

SPEED-700

RPMTOTALDEFORMA

TION

EQUVALENTSTRESS

EQUVALENTSTRESS

EQUVALENTSTRAIN

EQUVALENTSTRAIN

AT SPEED-1000
RPMTOTALDEFORMA
TION

AT SPEED-1200
RPMTOTALDEFORMA
TION

EQUIVALENTSTRESS

EQUIVALENTSTRESS

EQUIVALENTSTRAIN

EQUIVALENTSTRAIN

Case 3: HEXAGONAL
TOOLATSPEED-700 RPM
TOTALDEFORMATION

EQUIVALENTSTRESS

EQUIVALENTSTRAIN

AT SPEED-1000
RPMTOTALDEFORMA
TION

EQUIVALENTSTRESS

EQUIVALENTSTRAIN

AT SPEED-1200
RPMTOTALDEFORMA
TION

Heatflux

CASE2-TAPER TOOL

Temperature

Heatflux

CASE3-HEXAGONAL TOOL

Temperature

Heatflux

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Result Tables

Shape of tool	Tool rotational speed (RPM)	Deformation (mm)	Stress (N/mm ²)	Strain
Round	700	0.00018905	1.6929	9.5856e-6
	1000	0.00038581	3.4548	1.9562e-5
	1200	0.00055557	4.975	2.817e-5
Taper	700	0.00019177	1.243	1.2981e-5
	1000	0.00039138	2.538	2.6419e-5
	1200	0.00056358	3.654	3.8147e-5
Hexagonal	700	0.00019316	1.5368	1.2019e-5
	1000	0.0003942	3.1364	2.4528e-5
	1200	0.00056765	4.5164	3.5321e-5

Table 5.1-static analysis results

Shape of tool	Temperature (°C)		Heat flux (W/mm ²)
	Min	Max	
Round	25.26	131.65	1.5876
Taper	25.27	131.86	1.5604
Hexagonal	25.27	131.74	1.5912

Table 5.2-

Graphs

According to the above plot shows, deformation versus different tool rotational speeds and shapes. The maximum deformation at tool shape of hexagonal and tool rotational speed is 1200 RPM.

According to the above plot shows, stress versus different tool rotational speeds and shapes. The minimum stress at tool shape of taper and tool rotational speed is 700 RPM when we compared to other tool geometries and speeds.

According to the above plot shows, strain versus different tool rotational speeds and shapes. The maximum strain at tool shape of taper and tool rotational speed is 1200 RPM when we compare to other tool geometries and speeds.

According to the above plot shows, heat flux versus different tool shapes. The maximum heat flux at hexagonal tool when we compared to the round and taper tools.

6. CONCLUSIONS

- Structural analysis is performed on the different implement pin profiles at different speeds to verify the deformation, stress and strain. Thermal analysis is performed on the different implement pin profiles to verify the temperature distribution and heat flux.
- By optically canvassing the static analysis results, the stress values are decreased by decreasing the implement rotational speeds at taper pin profile when we compared to other implement geometries and speeds.

- By visually examining the thermal analysis results, the heat flux value more at the hexagonal implements shape when compared to other implement shapes.

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